

Behaviour of Electrolytes in Mixed Solvents Part XIII. Viscosity of Magnesium Sulphate and Zinc Sulphate in Dioxane-water Mixtures at 35°

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Viscosities of magnesium sulphate and zinc sulphate in dioxane-water mixtures at 0, 10, and 20% by weight of dioxane have been studied at 35°. The data fit well with the modified form of the Jones-Dole equation. The values of 'B' have been found to be dependent on the solvent composition, but the additive character has been noticed.

The application of the modified Jones-Dole equation¹, proposed by the present workers in cases of monovalent, uni-bivalent, and bi-univalent electrolytes² in dioxane-water mixtures at 35°, has been extended to bi-bivalent salts like magnesium sulphate and zinc sulphate, viscosities of which have been measured in 0, 10, and 20% dioxane-water mixtures at 35°.

EXPERIMENTAL

Magnesium sulphate and zinc sulphate used were of B.D.H. AnalaR quality. The Mg²⁺, Zn²⁺, and SO₄²⁻ contents were analysed by standard methods³. The viscometer used was of the type used by Chackravarty and Prasad⁴. The preparation of the solvents and solutions were the same as reported earlier². Sufficient care was taken to check the evaporation by the method used by Acharya *et al.*⁵. Viscosity and conductance were measured as described previously⁵.

TABLE II

Wt. % of dioxane,	Magnesium sulphate.			Zinc sulphate.			$\Delta B.$
	$A \times 10^2.$	$B.$	$x.$	$A \times 10^2.$	$B.$	$x.$	
0	2.70	0.59	1.00	2.60	0.57	1.00	0.02
10	2.95	0.69	1.01	2.90	0.70	0.99	-0.01
20	3.13	0.76	1.03	3.10	0.81	1.01	-0.05

DISCUSSION

The results have been expressed in the modified Jones-Dole equation:

$$1 + A\sqrt{C} + BC^2$$

where the terms have their usual significance. The terms have been calculated as described previously². These values are tabulated in Table I. The relative viscosities have been

1. Patnaik and Das, *Curr. Sci.*, 1956, **25**, 337.
2. Padhy and Das, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1963, **26**, 84.
3. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Analysis".
4. *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1939, **35**, 1460.
5. *This Journal*, 1957, **37**, 56.

TABLE II

Concn.	A. Salt = MgSO ₄ .				B. Salt = ZnSO ₄ .							
	0 % Dioxane.		20% Dioxane.		0 % Dioxane.		10 % Dioxane.		20% Dioxane.			
	Obs.	Calc.	Obs.	Calc.	Obs.	Calc.	Obs.	Calc.	Obs.	Calc.		
0.100	1.0675	1.0675	1.0771	1.0767	1.0807	1.0808	1.0650	1.0652	1.0813	1.0808	1.0894	1.0899
0.075	1.0511	1.0515	1.0586	1.0585	1.0614	1.0613	1.0501	1.0489	1.0616	1.0618	1.0679	1.0677
0.050	1.0356	1.0355	1.0410	1.0401	1.0411	1.0417	1.0348	1.0343	1.0424	1.0425	1.0460	1.0662
0.025	1.0208	1.0191	1.0204	1.0219	1.0216	1.0219	1.0182	1.0184	1.0227	1.0228	1.0248	1.0244
0.010	1.0087	1.0088	1.0090	1.0095	1.0098	1.0097	1.0083	1.0083	1.0096	1.0097	1.0104	1.0108
0.0075	1.0064	1.0067	1.0069	1.0075	1.0076	1.0076	1.0067	1.0066	1.0076	1.0080	1.0082	1.0084
0.005	1.0040	1.0049	1.0047	1.0053	1.0064	1.0055	1.0048	1.0047	1.0059	1.0058	1.0048	1.0050
0.0025	1.0024	1.0026	1.0027	1.0031	1.0032	1.0031	1.0023	1.0027	1.0028	1.0032	1.0026	1.0034

calculated by the determined values of 'B' and 'x' (Table II) and are in good agreement with the observed ones. The viscosities of MgSO_4 and ZnSO_4 at 30% solvent composition have been measured, but the value of the relative viscosity⁴ (η/η_0) has been found to be less than that of the value $1 + A\sqrt{C}$.

From the large number of experimental data available from the measurements of the aqueous solutions of various electrolytes, the nature of the term 'B' has been explained from various angles, namely, additive character of 'B', leading to computation of ionic values by Cox and Wolfenden⁵ and Kaminsky⁷ and lyotropic number by Asmus⁸.

In the studies made with the solvents containing dioxane-water mixtures as well as in the present investigation, the value of 'B' term progressively increases with increase of the dioxane content of the medium. The additive nature of 'B', which has been found by electrolytes in aqueous solution, is not noticed in the cases of the two electrolytes in the solvents studied (Table I). While taking into account the behaviour of electrolytes in mixed solvent containing large proportion of water, not only the behaviour of the ions in water is to be considered but also the influence of the third kind of molecule, namely, dioxane, is to be kept in picture. The extent to which 'B' values undergo change from medium to medium will depend on the role of the dioxane molecules played around a charged particle with respect to water in constituting the solvation sphere around the ion in question. In the immediate vicinity of small divalent positive ions, it is very probable that the water molecules with a permanent dipole will be firmly attached round the ion and the dioxane molecule may not get an equal chance to be attached to the ion. Since the evidence⁹ is quite feasible to show that the solvation sphere is constituted with both kinds of molecules present in the medium, it is quite consistent to expect that beyond the firmly bound water molecules, there exists a region composed of both the water and the dioxane molecules. It may be expected that this orientation depends on the size of the ions, their charge, and the relative presence of water molecules and dioxane molecules in this sphere of orientation. Assuming that the SO_4^{2-} in both the electrolytes, MgSO_4 and ZnSO_4 , behave in a similar manner and the relative availability of the dioxane and water molecules being the same for a particular solvent (say for 10% of dioxane and 90% of water), Mg^{2+} with its small size does have a greater influence in ordering orientation of the water and dioxane molecules than the Zn^{2+} , and hence two different 'B' values are expected for the two electrolytes in the same medium. It is quite reasonable to expect the cations to show preferential treatment to one kind of molecules, possibly water, in ordering the orientation in the second layer and this orientation need not be the same even though the charge of the two ions in question may be the same. Therefore, when the dioxane and water contents of the solvent are changed, the two ions orient the available water and dioxane molecules in different proportion and it is not surprising to find the additive relation of 'B' is broken down in mixed solvents, specially when the dioxane content increases.

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6. *Proc Roy. Soc.*, 1934, **145A**, 45.
7. *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1957, **12a**, 424.
8. *Ibid.*, 1949, **4a**, 589.
9. Das, *this Journal*, 1959, **36**, 813.